

Cramer-Rao Inequality for Fisher Information And Zeros of the Wavefunction

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The Cramer-Rao inequality (which is based on a Cauchy-Schwarz result for inner products of vectors) links spatial variance to Fisher information. The inner products are integrals in this case, and it seems the entire bound state space is utilised and use is made of a vanishing wavefunction at endpoints. It seems, however, the wavefunction may vanish at other points if it is periodic, such as for an oscillator or a particle in a box. In such a case, it seems one could use Fisher information to analyze density humps and obtain information about the variance of x within such a hump, with the origin shifted to the center of the hump. In particular, as energy levels rise, the zeroes come close together and one may associate the envelope of quantum density $W(x)W(x)$ ($W(x)$ =wavefunction) with $C/v(x)$ ($v(x)$ = classical velocity). Thus, at very high energy levels, one may combine Fisher information with the correspondence principle to obtain information about spatial quantum variance in terms of classical quantities.

Fisher Information and the Cramer-Rao Inequality

Spatial Fisher information is given, in one dimension, by:

$$F = \int dx W(x)W(x) \left[\frac{d}{dx} \ln(W(x)W(x)) \right]^2 \quad ((1))$$

The Cramer-Rao inequality, in (1), is derived using the Cauchy-Schwarz result for the inner product of vectors, with the inner product here being the integral weighted by $W(x)W(x)$.

$$\sqrt{\text{Var}(x)} \sqrt{\text{Var}(B)} \geq \text{Cov}(x, B) \quad \text{where } B(x) = \frac{d}{dx} \ln(W(x)W(x)) \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{Cov}(x, B) = \int dx W(x)W(x) x \frac{d}{dx} \ln[W(x)W(x)] = \int dx W(x) x \frac{d}{dx} W(x) \quad ((3))$$

Here x is over the bound state range. Now:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \{ x W(x)W(x) \} = W(x)W(x) + x \frac{d}{dx} [W(x)W(x)] \quad ((4))$$

Integrating ((4)) gives zero for the LHS because $W(x)$ vanishes at the endpoints. The integral of $W(x)W(x)$ is 1 because density is normalized. Thus, $\text{cov}(x, B) = -1$ and one obtains:

$$\sqrt{\text{Var}(x)} \geq 1 / \sqrt{\text{Fisher information}}.$$

In addition, one may use:

$$d/dx \{ W d/dx W \} = (d/dx W)^2 + W d/dx d/dx W \quad ((5))$$

The integral on the LHS of ((5)) is zero because W vanishes at the endpoints. The first integral on the RHS is Fisher information and the second is $(-2m) \cdot \hbar^2 v(x) W(x)W(x)$, where $v(x)$ is classical velocity. Thus:

$$\text{Fisher Information} = \text{Integral } (1/2m) \cdot \hbar^2 v(x) v(x) W(x)W(x) dx \quad ((6))$$

Form ((6)) is convenient for use with the correspondence principle, i.e. $W(x)W(x)$ is replaced by an envelope function of $C/v(x)$.

Fisher Information Between Zeroes of $W(x)$

It seems $W(x)$ may be periodic in many cases, such as the oscillator and particle in a box. In such cases, $W(x)$ vanishes at its zeros and one should be able to apply the ideas above to the "hump" in the density, although $\text{Cov}(x,B)$ will change. In particular, one should be able to apply the Cramer-Rao inequality to the high energy limit and find information about the spatial x variance in terms of classical quantities.

For the high energy limit, one replaces $W(x)W(x)$ with the envelope function $C/v(x)$.

Consider a small hump of width dx which is infinitesimal at very high energies. Then:

$$\text{Cov}(x, b) = \text{Integral } dx W(x)W(x) = C/v(x) dx \quad \text{instead of } 1 \text{ for the whole } x \text{ range. Thus:}$$

$$\text{Sqrt}(\text{Var}(x)) \geq dx C/v(x) / [\text{Sqrt}(\text{Fisher Information})] \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{Fisher information} = 1/4 \text{ Integral } dx v(x)v(x) C/v(x) = dx C/v(x) v(x)v(x)$$

If one places the origin at the center of the "hump", between the two zeroes of $W(x)$, then

$$\text{Var}(x) = \text{Integral } x^2 W(x)W(x) dx = dx dx dx b C/v(x) \text{ where } b \text{ is a number.}$$

Thus:

$$dx \text{ sqrt}(b) = 2/ v(x) \quad ((8))$$

$$\text{The width } dx \text{ is of the order of } 1/v(x) \text{ and } \text{Var}(x) = \{ 2/[v(x) \text{ sqrt}(b)] \}^3 C/v(x) \text{ and } \text{sqrt}(\text{Var}(x)) \text{ is proportional to } [1/v(x)]^2 \quad ((9))$$

For a particle in a box, $W(x) = C_1 \sin(kx-b)$ so $\hbar^2 v(x)v(x) = \hbar^2 k^2$. Thus $1/v(x)$ is of the order $1/k$ or proportional to the wavelength. For a particle in a box, $\text{Var}(x)$ is of the order of $1/k^3$ because C is of the order of k .

For the oscillator, it is suggested that in the very high energy limit, the humps have a width dx proportional to $1/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is the classical velocity and $\text{Var}(x)$

Fisher Information and Change in Density

Relationship ((5)) links Fisher information with kinetic energy density. This is interesting as there seem to be two velocities in quantum mechanics, for all energy levels. The first is the root mean square kinetic energy velocity:

$$[\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p^2/2m \text{ } \int \exp(ipx)] / W(x) = (-1/2m) [d/dx d/dx W(x)] / W(x) = .5m v(x)v(x) \quad ((10))$$

Here $v(x)$ is classical velocity which is associated with time according to $dx = v(x) dt_1$ for a tiny distance dx . For quantum mechanics, at least at low energy levels, it is not clear that dt_1 has any meaning. There is another velocity:

$$[\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p \int \exp(ipx)] / W(x) = m u(x) \text{ and } d/dx [W(x)W(x)] = 2 W(x)W(x) m u(x) \quad ((11))$$

The flux velocity $u(x)$ is related to density changes. Usually $u(x)$ is not equal to $v(x)$, but one has $dx = u(x) dt_2$ so it seems there is another time scale in the system related to dt_2 . In this case, it may have some physical significance as it is related to average momentum flow.

In general $W(x)W(x) .5m u(x)u(x)$ is not equal to $W(x)W(x) .5m v(x)v(x)$, but the integral of the two are identical as shown by ((5)). This is due to the wavefunction vanishing at the boundaries. Thus, the same ideas apply to the “hump” region between two zeroes in $W(x)$. The integral of $W(x)W(x) u(x)u(x)$ is Fisher’s information. As energy levels become very high, humps become very small and $W(x)W(x) .5 m u(x)u(x)$ is almost equal to $W(x)W(x) .5 m v(x)v(x)$. In such a case, flux velocity (or matter flow velocity) and energy velocity become very similar and quantum mechanics seems to enter the “classical” region.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems ideas used in the derivation of the Cramer-Rao inequality linking $\text{Var}(x)$ to Fisher information make use of the wavefunction vanishing at boundary points. Thus, much of the derivation, it seems, applies to a “hump” region between zeros of $W(x)$. In such a case, however, $\int W(x)W(x) dx$ is not 1 because the region is only a portion of the whole range of x and $\text{Cov}(x, B)$ where $B = d/dx \ln(W(x))$ needs to be modified. It seems that as energy levels become very high, the hump regions become small, almost infinitesimal and one can replace $W(x)W(x)$ with $C/v(x)$ and estimate the integral as dx times Function value. In such a case, Fisher information $W(x)W(x) \{d/dx W/W\} \{d/dx W/ W\}$ equals $W(x) d/dx d/dx W(x)$ and

$m u(x) = d/dx W/W$ is identical to $m v(x)$ where $.5mv(x)v(x)$ is the classical kinetic energy. In such a case, the two velocities $u(x)$ related to flux flow and $v(x)$ related to kinetic energy motion are associated with the same dt and the two flows are synchronous. One has, it seems, classical behaviour.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cram%C3%A9r%E2%80%93Rao_bound